

Korzhevskyi Oleksandr,
5th-year student of higher medical education
Bukovinian State Medical University,
Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Pecheriaha Svitlana,
Candidate of Medical Sciences, Assistant
Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology and Perinatology,
Bukovinian State Medical University,
Chernivtsi, Ukraine
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20152641>

HORMONAL REGULATION OF LACTATION AND MECHANISMS OF LACTATIONAL AMENORRHEA

Коржевський Олександр Ігорович,
здобувач вищої медичної освіти, 5 курс
Буковинський державний медичний університет
м. Чернівці, Україна
Печеряга Світлана Володимирівна,
кандидатка медичних наук, асистентка
кафедри акушерства, гінекології та перинатології
Буковинський державний медичний університет,
м. Чернівці, Україна

ГОРМОНАЛЬНА РЕГУЛЯЦІЯ ЛАКТАЦІЇ ТА МЕХАНІЗМИ ЛАКТАЦІЙНОЇ АМЕНОРЕЇ

Abstract

The postpartum period is an important stage in a woman's life, characterized by complex physiological and hormonal changes aimed at restoring the body after pregnancy and ensuring nourishment of the newborn. This article presents a synthesis of current scientific data on the mechanisms underlying the initiation and maintenance of lactation, as well as the peculiarities of hormonal regulation during the puerperium. Particular attention is paid to the role of prolactin and oxytocin in the processes of milk synthesis and ejection, as well as to the significance of autocrine mechanisms in the regulation of lactation. The physiological basis of lactational amenorrhea as a natural method of contraception, based on the suppression of pituitary gonadotropic function, is discussed. The influence of early mother–infant contact, feeding frequency, and pharmacological factors on lactation effectiveness is analyzed. The findings emphasize the importance of supporting breastfeeding and adopting an individualized approach to the management of women in the postpartum period.

Анотація

Післяпологовий період є важливим етапом у житті жінки, що характеризується складними фізіологічними та гормональними змінами, спрямованими на відновлення організму після вагітності та забезпечення вигодовування новонародженого. У статті представлено узагальнення сучасних наукових даних щодо механізмів становлення та підтримання лактації, а також особливостей гормональної регуляції у пuerperії. Особливу увагу приділено ролі пролактину та окситоцину у процесах синтезу та виділення молока, а також значенню аутокринних механізмів регуляції лактації. Розглянуто фізіологічні основи лактаційної аменореї як природного методу контрацепції, що базується на пригніченні гонадотропної функції гіпофіза. Проаналізовано вплив раннього контакту матері та дитини, частоти годувань і фармакологічних факторів на ефективність лактації. Отримані дані підкреслюють важливість підтримки грудного вигодовування та індивідуалізованого підходу до ведення жінок у післяпологовому періоді.

Keywords: postpartum period, lactation, prolactin, oxytocin, lactational amenorrhea, breastfeeding, hormonal regulation, lactogenesis, lactopoiesis.

Ключові слова: postpartum period, lactation, prolactin, oxytocin, lactational amenorrhea, breastfeeding, hormonal regulation, lactogenesis, lactopoiesis.

Introduction. The postpartum period (puerperium) is a unique stage in a woman's life that begins after the delivery of the placenta and lasts on average 6–8 weeks, during which the body gradually returns to its pre-pregnancy state. During this time, a complex reorganization of the functions of nearly all organs and systems occurs, including the cardiovascular, endocrine,

reproductive, and immune systems. Particular importance is attributed to uterine involution, normalization of hormonal homeostasis, and adaptation of metabolic mechanisms to new conditions [1, 3]. A central role in the postpartum period is played by the initiation and maintenance of lactation - a complex biological process that ensures optimal nutrition, immunological

protection, and harmonious development of the newborn. Breastfeeding is considered not only a physiological process but also a socially significant one, with proven short- and long-term benefits for both the infant and the mother. However, despite current recommendations for exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months of life, its global prevalence remains insufficient, underscoring the relevance of in-depth research into the mechanisms of lactation [4]. Hormonal restructuring serves as the driving force behind these processes, ensuring the transition from pregnancy to the state of a lactating mother [6]. Understanding these mechanisms is fundamental for providing high-quality obstetric care and supporting breastfeeding [7].

Aim of the study. The aim of this study is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of current scientific data on the physiological mechanisms of lactation and the *особенности* of hormonal regulation in the postpartum period.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted through an analysis of current scientific publications, recommendations of international organizations, and results of clinical studies focused on the physiology of the postpartum period and lactation.

Results and discussion. The World Health Organization (WHO) currently recommends exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months, as increasing evidence demonstrates both short- and long-term health benefits. However, recent data indicate that only about 40% of mothers worldwide achieve this goal (WHO and UNICEF, 2017).

Lactation is a complex biological process conventionally divided into several phases: lactogenesis (initiation of milk secretion), lactopoiesis (maintenance of secretion), and involution (cessation of lactation) [4].

During puberty, increased levels of estrogen and progesterone stimulate the development of new alveolar buds, which subsequently form the milk-secreting lobules of the mammary gland. During pregnancy, the volume of breast tissue increases, accompanied by active formation of new alveolar-lobular structures and further functional maturation of the milk-producing system. Estrogen, progesterone, and prolactin are essential for this development during pregnancy. However, other factors, including placental lactogen and growth hormone, also play a role. During pregnancy, little or no milk is produced because high levels of progesterone and estrogen inhibit the secretory activity of alveolar cells. During labor and lactation, further growth and differentiation occur, increasing the glandular component of the mammary gland [6].

The onset of milk production occurs 2–4 days after delivery [1]. The expulsion of the placenta leads to a sharp decline in progesterone and estrogen levels [3]. This “unmasking” effect allows prolactin, whose levels remain elevated, to fully initiate the secretion of transitional and subsequently mature milk [5].

Prolactin is the key hormone responsible for milk secretion (the prolactin reflex) [4]. Its release is stimulated by mechanical irritation of nerve endings in the nipple and areola during infant suckling [9]. Prolactin acts on the alveolar cells of the mammary gland, stimulating the synthesis of milk proteins,

lactose, and fats [7]. Importantly, prolactin levels in the blood are highest at night, emphasizing the importance of nighttime feedings for maintaining lactation [2].

Oxytocin is responsible for milk ejection (the oxytocin reflex, or milk let-down reflex) [1]. Its secretion, like that of prolactin, is triggered by nipple stimulation but can also be induced by psycho-emotional factors, such as the sound of a baby crying or even thinking about the infant [10]. Oxytocin causes contraction of the myoepithelial cells surrounding the alveoli, pushing milk into the ducts and toward the nipple [3]. This sensation is commonly described by women as the “milk let-down” [1].

Lactopoiesis (maintenance of lactation) is regulated by the principle of “supply and demand” [5]. The more frequently and effectively the breast is emptied, the greater the milk production [8]. This is a local, autocrine mechanism regulated by the Feedback Inhibitor of Lactation (FIL), present in milk [9]. If milk remains in the gland, the concentration of FIL increases, suppressing further secretion [4].

An intact hypothalamic–pituitary regulatory axis controlling prolactin and oxytocin levels is essential for the initiation and maintenance of lactation. Lactation requires both the synthesis of milk and its secretion into the alveoli and lactiferous sinuses. When milk is not removed, increased intramammary pressure reduces capillary blood flow and inhibits lactation. Absence of suckling stimulation results in the lack of prolactin release from the pituitary gland. The basal level of prolactin, which rises in response to suckling-induced surges, is necessary to maintain lactation during the first weeks postpartum. However, without oxytocin, although pregnancy can be carried to term, lactation cannot occur due to the absence of milk ejection.

Hormonal changes in the postpartum period also stimulate uterine involution [10]. Oxytocin released during breastfeeding acts not only on the mammary glands but also on the myometrium, inducing its contraction [3]. This promotes uterine involution and reduces postpartum bleeding [6]. This process is particularly noticeable in multiparous women as painful uterine contractions during breastfeeding [1].

During the period of intensive lactation, most women experience physiological lactational amenorrhea [2]. Elevated prolactin levels suppress the pulsatile release of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) from the hypothalamus [7]. This, in turn, leads to decreased secretion of luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) by the pituitary gland, inhibiting follicular maturation and ovulation [5]. Thus, prolactin acts as a natural contraceptive (the lactational amenorrhea method, LAM) [8]. The restoration of the menstrual cycle begins after a reduction in feeding frequency, usually after 4–6 months [4]. In women who do not breastfeed, the menstrual cycle resumes much earlier—approximately within 8–10 weeks [1].

In the postpartum period, there is also a gradual normalization of thyroid and adrenal gland function, which were altered during pregnancy [10]. Glucocorticoid levels decrease but remain sufficient to support milk synthesis [9].

Skin-to-skin contact is a modern standard of childbirth care [2]. It not only promotes colonization of the newborn with maternal microbiota but also has a critical impact on hormonal regulation [5]. This contact, along with early initiation of breastfeeding (within the first hour), stimulates a strong release of oxytocin and prolactin, ensuring a successful onset of lactogenesis [1].

Pharmacological correction of lactation is used infrequently. Lactation stimulants (galactagogues) may be indicated in cases of true hypogalactia [10]. Domperidone is one of the drugs used off-label to increase prolactin levels by blocking dopamine receptors [3]. However, the most effective and safest стимулятором lactation remains frequent and effective breast emptying [7].

Hormonal contraception during lactation requires careful consideration. Combined oral contraceptives (COCs) containing estrogen may negatively affect milk volume [6]. Therefore, progestin-only contraceptives are the recommended choice for breastfeeding women [9].

Conclusions. The postpartum period is a complex and dynamic physiological stage characterized by profound hormonal changes aimed at restoring the body after pregnancy and ensuring effective lactation. Prolactin and oxytocin play a key role in the initiation and maintenance of lactation by regulating milk synthesis and ejection, respectively. The effectiveness of lactation largely depends on the frequency and completeness of breast emptying, mediated by autocrine regulatory mechanisms. An important physiological consequence of intensive lactation is lactational amenorrhea, which serves as a natural contraceptive mechanism through suppression of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis under the influence of elevated prolactin levels. Early skin-to-skin contact and timely initiation of breastfeeding are crucial for the onset of lactogenesis and stabilization of hormonal regulation. Thus, understanding the physiological mechanisms of the postpartum period is essential for optimizing medical care, supporting breastfeeding, and preserving women's reproductive health.

References:

1. Schwartz, E., & Ketner Villa, J. (2025). Navigating the Postpartum Period: Hormonal Changes and Essential Care for Women. In *Obstetrics and Gynecology*. *IntechOpen*.
<https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.1008428>

2. Schlesinger, E., Hatiel, K., Hod, N., & Shinwell, E.S. (2024). Longer skin-to-skin contact after birth enhances breastfeeding quality and duration: A cohort study. *Acta Paediatr*, *113*, 2637–2642. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apa.17388>

3. Augustine, R. A., Ladyman, S. R., Bouwer, G. T., Alyousif, Y., Sapsford, T. J., Scott, V., Kokay, I. C., Grattan, D. R., & Brown, C. H. (2017). Prolactin regulation of oxytocin neurone activity in pregnancy and lactation. *The Journal of physiology*, *595*(11), 3591–3605. <https://doi.org/10.1113/JP273712>

4. Zhou, X., Ullah, A., Shi, L., Dou, M., Wang, C., Khan, M. Z., Wang, C., & Zhang, X. (2025). Molecular Regulatory Mechanisms of Mammary Gland Development: A Review. *Animals: an open access journal from MDPI*, *15*(23), 3480. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani15233480>

5. Weaver, S. R., & Hernandez, L. L. (2016). Autocrine-paracrine regulation of the mammary gland. *Journal of dairy science*, *99*(1), 842–853. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-9828>

6. Stanton, T. A., & Blumenthal, P. D. (2019). Postpartum hormonal contraception in breastfeeding women. *Current opinion in obstetrics & gynecology*, *31*(6), 441–446. <https://doi.org/10.1097/GCO.0000000000000571>

7. Calik-Ksepka, A., Stradczuk, M., Czarnecka, K., Grymowicz, M., & Smolarczyk, R. (2022). Lactational Amenorrhea: Neuroendocrine Pathways Controlling Fertility and Bone Turnover. *International journal of molecular sciences*, *23*(3), 1633. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23031633>

8. Vila-Candel, R., Soriano-Vidal, F. J., Franco-Antonio, C., Garcia-Algar, O., Andreu-Fernandez, V., & Mena-Tudela, D. (2024). Factors Influencing Duration of Breastfeeding: Insights from a Prospective Study of Maternal Health Literacy and Obstetric Practices. *Nutrients*, *16*(5), 690. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu16050690>

9. Lebedevs, T. & Kendrick, C. (2019). Pharmacological management of common lactation problems. *J Pharm Pract Res*, *49*, 192-198. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jppr.1561>

10. Crowley, W.R. (2014). Neuroendocrine Regulation of Lactation and Milk Production. *Comprehensive Physiology*, *5*.